

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGICAL CRITICAL THINKING AND THE FORMATION OF DISCOURSAL COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article raises the need to assess the level of critical thinking and the use of didactics in educational processes with younger students in educational institutions. The research follows a qualitative approach and phenomenological hermeneutics. The design sought to explore, describe, and understand the phenomenon based on the experiences of the participants to discover the common elements of those experiences. To design the study, we worked with individuals who agreed to participate in the pandemic and had access to researchers using a semi-structured interview and checklist with a sample of 10 students and 3 faculty members. institution; the elements were aimed at reaching the domains indicated in the studied categories. It can be concluded that the level of thinking of younger students is still developing since it is still difficult for them to substantiate their thoughts with arguments. Likewise, teachers know that they need to deeply analyze the texts or content being studied so that students can find hidden meanings that cause problems and develop realistic and contextual thinking skills.

Keywords: discursive competence, critical thinking, sequential learning, analysis, realistic thinking.

Introduction. Society is continually changing, to that end training can't be abandoned and should complete a similar cycle to guarantee that learners foster abilities to think, observe, contend and act basically in different circumstances and settings. The school should have the vision set on the arrangement of free and dependable residents who with their decisive reasoning keep away from any instrument of control and double-dealing. Concentrates on how decisive reasoning abilities can be created from didactics are developing consistently. In a specific order of thoughts, crafted by others no less significant will be huge and important. exceptionally youthful age In the development of people, it is fundamental that the improvement of decisive reasoning abilities is advanced from an extremely youthful age [1.53]. Consequently, it is fitting to begin this cycle in grade school, so learners can confront the troublesome settings where they reside with contentions; to figure out how to break down, grasp, contend

and propose elective arrangements or pursue choices from motivation to assist them with excelling; this, without allowing others to exploit what is going on, lie to them, settle on choices for them or, bombing that, control them. Similarly, the advancement of decisive reasoning abilities accuses the individual of individual yet sensible decisions, which assist them with further developing their present and future, as dynamic individuals that add to the change of society. Kids think inductively and logically sometimes before they start their language; and are keen on knowing the why of things, which is the reason they are viewed as regular scholars. This craving to second guesses themselves reduces when they grow up; notwithstanding, interest remains[2.36].

Along these lines, this review was meant to assess the degree of decisive reasoning and the utilization of didactics in the education educational experiences with grade school learners. While surveying the writing, it was valued that there are not many doctoral examinations at the public level on the advancement of decisive reasoning abilities in learners at this level. Campos, as far as it matters for him, characterizes decisive reasoning as thinking obviously and from reason, which leans toward the improvement of intelligent and free reasoning, which empowers each person to make solid decisions about the believability of an assertion. Or then again if an activity as he would see it is advantageous or not. This trained mental cycle utilizes procedures and thinking that individuals use to assess contentions, simply decide, make decisions, what's more, and learn new things. Accordingly, decisive reasoning is a scholarly action that permits the advancement of mental capacities to conceptualize, examine circumstances and data, arrange thoughts, distinguish, guard contentions, notice and make determinations; that permits them to reflect and convey looking for their improvement and that of the climate where they work. For Torres, decisive reasoning alludes to the scholarly abilities that the subject purposes to dissect, decipher, check, analyze regardless of whether something is solid, and tackle issues utilizing correspondence however continuously placing in I express their situation or perspective before it[3.144].

Accordingly, fostering this ability to think is vital because it assists people with thinking, comprehending, and acting dependably and really on the thing that is known; deliberate reflection, makes the subject express something from their past information and the examination of resided encounters that are tried, to have the option to perceive and pursue right choices where mentalities of flexibility are gained notwithstanding affliction, which makes conceivable to extend themselves as dynamic and change pioneers in their networks. The

growing experience from its development started with the behaviorist hypothesis, where the job of the educator was of the transmitter of information and that of the understudy of the simple collector; Later, with constructivism, the chance was opened for the understudy to advance by doing, or at least, to play a main part in the educating educational experience; and the instructor here would be an aide or middle person so the understudy, along with him and his cohorts, could helpfully change his insight. It is hence that the showing system is connected with procedures or exercises that the educator performs so learners obtain learning and accomplish their instructive objectives[4.125]; Helping alludes to activities, methodologies, or exercises completed by the instructor to communicate information, which is straightforwardly connected to the philosophy, characteristics, and conduct of learners, and their readiness to realize; this makes various associations conceivable: the information they get from their instructors; that is, information on various disciplines that blend in with their pre-information, the truth and encounters of the quick climate (family, companions, gatherings of interest, and so forth); consequently advancing the expert and individual improvement of every person. Hence, for Loudon and Franco, the educational experience is straightforwardly connected with the modes or ways that learners use to incorporate or realize, which incorporates variation and consequently change in conduct as per their encounters inside and beyond the school setting. The educating educational experience is conceived and grows inside and socially, for which it addresses a collaboration situated and in light of specific expectations, on self-reflection and decisive reasoning of the entertainers associated with the cycle; This begins in any climate; at school, it is completed with the showing system, academic procedures are utilized focused on looking for learning, character development and begin foundation social changes. For figuring out how to happen in a palatable manner, the educator needs to consider the learners' pre-information, or at least, all that gathering of ideas or information that youngsters now have and that they have gained as far as they can tell because of social connections or encounters with others; Similarly, the instructor should utilize differed, dynamic and appealing showing techniques, which are persuading and permit the absorption of realizing, where the techniques are adaptable, dynamic and permit intuitiveness, with the goal that the youngster fabricates their ideas, their learning. Accordingly, the educator through the direction of the exercises should utilize systems and methodology that make them learn, and assist with laying out decisive considerations and positions; In like manner, it is applicable that

during this cycle the understudy feels propelled to realize, which further develops their confidence so they do it with delight, hopefulness and partake all the while [5.224].

Conclusion. The examination showed that the degree of reasoning of grade school learners is created because it is as yet hard for them to contend their thoughts from reason; Similarly, educators know that they should do more top to bottom dissects of the texts or items concentrated so learners find covered up or certain implications that produce concerns. The degree of decisive reasoning is reinforced while the school personnel is prepared, pedantic go, and utilizes propelling methodologies so learners through consistent reflection foster reasoning abilities. Moreover, with the improvement of educational activities that animate the faculties, and support understanding, where different materials and techniques are planned and applied so learners figure out how to reason about the real world, giving way to imagination and to be dynamic learning elements; Decisive reasoning can be enabled in learners, which should be a cycle done in a cognizant manner to advance a social arousing and wipe out strings of force, being important to advance it in the study hall with genuine and contextualized circumstances that spur them to give basic contentions. Didactics is the fundamental pivot of the educating educational experience, it is made out of arranging, helping, and assessing; so that, the utilization of pedantic procedures where deduction, argumentation, suggestion, examination, and comprehension of circumstances or occasions are utilized; Perceiving in them their correspondence purposes and aims are compelling in creating decisive reasoning abilities in learners [6.39].

At long last, the educating growing experience should be an intelligent space where information with an elevated degree of importance is fabricated; that utilizes displays, discussions, play and cooperation, described by inspiration, connection, understanding, and critical thinking; which are sufficient pedantic procedures for learners to gain huge information and foster decisive reasoning abilities to be applied in genuine settings, where they can form decisions, tackle issues, reflect and contend to propose or settle circumstances in their current circumstance [7.201].

References:

1. Moreno-Pinado, W. & Velázquez, M. (2017). Didactic Strategy to Develop Critical Thinking. REICE-Ibero-American Journal on Quality, Efficacy, and Change in Education, 15, (2), 53-73. Madrid Spain. DOI: 10.15366 / reice2017.15.2.003.<https://revistas.uam.es/index.php/reice/article/view/7019>

2. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=55150357003>
3. Tenreiro-Vieira, C & Marques, R. (2019). Promote or Critical Thinking in Basic School Science: Proposals and Challenges. Latin American Journal of Educational Studies, 15 (1), 36-49. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17151/rlee.2019.15.1.3> Available at: <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=1341/134157920003>.
4. Angarita, J. (2018). Appropriation of augmented reality as support for the teaching of natural sciences in primary Basic education. Revista Boletín Redipe, 7, (12), 144-157. ISSN-e 2256-1536. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=6728828>
5. Zona-López, J. & Giraldo-Márquez, J. (2017). Problem-solving: critical thinking scenario in Science Didactics. Latin American Journal of Educational Studies (Colombia), 13 (2), 122-150. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17151/rlee.2017.13.2.8> Available at:
6. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=1341/134154501008>
7. Díaz, A. (2009). Think about the didactics. Amorrortu editors. Buenos Aires - Madrid. pp. 224. <https://docs.google.com/file/d/0ByY1BMds6LXabkZZZFNGTWNIZms/viEw>
8. Díaz, A. (2007). Didactics and curriculum. Editorial Paidós Educador. Mexico. pp.39. https://www.academia.edu/37159021/%C3%81ngel_D%C3%ADaz_Barriga_Did%C3%A1ctica_y_curr%C3%ADculum.
9. Torres, D., Fonseca, W. & Pineda, B. (2017). Experiences as a strategy to reinforce critical thinking in rural education. Praxis & Saber Magazine, 8 (17), 201-224. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.19053/22160159.v8.n17.2018.7207> Available at: <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=4772/477253330010>.

